
TECHNIQUES OF READING AND WORKING WITH TEXTS IN GERMAN LESSONS

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Abstract.

The need for reading lies not only in the practical mastery of a foreign language and culture, but is also a means of creative activity and self-education. The article deals with modern techniques of reading and working with texts in German lessons.

Keywords.

reading, methods, stages, formation of skills and abilities, communicative competence

Introduction:

Reading is an important skill for students of German as a second language and German as a foreign language. Understanding the meaning of these methods is essential for teachers who want to improve their lessons. It should be noted that in order to obtain an excellent result and master reading in German or another foreign language, students need to understand reading as a type of speech activity, a way of obtaining information and its further use. Reading should not be an exercise in voicing language material, memorizing it or translating it. The formation of skills and abilities in reading is a rather complex process and is one of the most important tasks in teaching foreign languages both in the past and in the present. However, it should be noted that at different stages of the development of human society and the formation of methodological science, teaching reading occupied a different place and was carried out in different ways. There are two sides to reading in the traditional method. It is customary to single out "understanding" and "reading technique".

Main part:

"Reading technique" is the ability of students to perceive and determine grapheme-phoneme relationships, combine material and use intonation. There is an opinion that German, due to the ambiguity of the pronunciation of words, is a problem for novice readers (N.A Izmailova, 2014).

Reading, as a type of speech activity, is focused on solving a communicative task, that is, on understanding what is read. It should not turn into a means of controlling the assimilation of vocabulary and grammar; the printed text should not be taken as a sample of oral expression for its subsequent reproduction works. In the process of reading, words, phrases, phraseological units, linguistic realities are involuntarily remembered, which later can be used in oral speech. The accumulation of linguistic material through reading is a consequence of this process, and not its special task. If the student knows that when reading, the teacher will check his knowledge of vocabulary or grammar, then the focus will inevitably be on language material [17, 27]. Instead of trying to perceive the material in blocks, the student will divide it into words, linger on each of them, and mentally check his knowledge of words, to lead them into their native language even when it is not required for reading comprehension. Fixing attention to the increasing linguistic form of the text negatively affects the development of the ability to read, as he rereads, makes unnecessary eye stops on each word, slows down the pace, reduces the scope of the text. This strengthens those skills that, when learning to read, must be eliminated. Repeated reading of the same text is inappropriate. If the content of the text is clear, then reading loses its communicative value and turns into simple voicing. Repeated reading is justified if it is aimed at clarifying understanding, that is, if the communicative task is modified (Bork; 2012: 76). The sound analytic-synthetic method is the most attractive against the background of all of the above. In this case, the teacher not only teaches children to pronounce sounds correctly, shows articulation, but also teaches them to analyze these words, reinforcing this process with the most commonly used reading rules in such a way that the student, faced with an unfamiliar word, can guess for himself, based on his knowledge, how it is read.

Let's move on to the consideration of the process of teaching reading not only from the point of view of learning the technique of reading, but also from the standpoint of learning to understand the meaning, or "actually reading". In the modern methodology, there are a variety of effective methods and techniques for teaching reading: a communicative-oriented, problem-based, differentiated method of teaching oral speech and reading, the whole text method, the verbal lead method, and critical thinking technologies.

The communicative approach plays an important role in teaching reading.. It is very important to form students' foreign language communicative competence, which is understood as language, speech and socio-cultural types [3, 14]. Achieving communicative competence involves mastering a certain amount of cultural

information, familiarization with the culture of the people whose language is being studied. The mastery of this information occurs with the help of textual material, which is subject to such requirements as content, information content, cognitive value.

The main task of reading is to consolidate the ability of students to extract useful information from the text they read, to instill in students a taste for independent reading of literature in a foreign language [37, 17].

An approximate algorithm for students to work with the title before reading any text.

Lesen Sie den Titel sorgfältig durch und markieren Sie das Schlüsselwort darin (meistens wird es durch ein Substantiv ausgedrückt).

Schauen Sie sich den Text an und achten Sie darauf, wie oft das dominante Wort des von Ihnen hervorgehobenen Titels im Text vorkommt.

Finden Sie Ersatzwörter für das dominante Wort und die gesamte Überschrift im Text.

Paraphrasieren Sie den Namen mit Synonymen aus dem Text.

Angebotsphase.

Geben Sie an, ob es einen Abschnitt gibt, der die Hauptthemen des Artikels auflistet.

Siehe Liste der behandelten Themen am Ende des einleitenden Teils des Artikels;

Überprüfen Sie den Text und sagen Sie, für welche Leserkategorie er von Interesse sein könnte und warum;

Geben Sie an, welchen der folgenden Themen im Artikel besondere Aufmerksamkeit gewidmet wird.

Markieren Sie Textpassagen, die Antworten auf die vorgeschlagenen Fragen geben;

Post-Text-Phase

Lesen Sie die Fakten zum Thema aus dem Text...;

Unterstreichen Sie die Definition (Schlussfolgerung, Begriff) im Text.

Nachdem die erforderlichen Informationen gefunden wurden, ist der Zweck der Suchlesung erreicht.

Übungen zum Erlernen des suchenden Lesens.

Identifizieren Sie das Thema oder die Fragestellung des Textes (Artikels);

Lesen Sie den Text und prüfen Sie, ob er die gestellten Fragen beantwortet. Finden Sie das Hauptargument für den Titel im Text.

Lesen Sie zwei Texte zum gleichen Thema, die auf inhaltliche Unterschiede hinweisen (Anzahl der angegebenen Fakten, unterschiedliche Einschätzungen etc.);

Finden Sie auf einer bestimmten Seite die Eigenschaften von Charakteren, Anweisungen, Rezepten, Empfehlungen usw.;

Überprüfen Sie die Zusammenfassung und prüfen Sie, ob sie mit dem Inhalt des Textes übereinstimmt.

Finden Sie Absätze zu einem bestimmten Thema.

Antworten auf Fragen im Text finden (was zu Schlussfolgerungen führt)

Schauen Sie sich das Bild an und benennen Sie den Absatz, den es darstellt.

Finden Sie im Text die Tatsachen, die der Autor positiv und negativ erwähnt;

Teilen Sie den Text entsprechend den Punkten des Plans in Teile auf;

Äußern Sie Ihre Meinung zum Inhalt des Textes und beziehen Sie diese auf Ihre eigenen Erfahrungen usw. ein.

The communicative goals of teaching reading involve the use of various types of text in the educational process - different genres and functional styles. The method of working on a foreign text contains a number of techniques that can be used to develop various reading skills [37, 19]. So, welcome, "multiple choice." Students are asked five questions on the text with four possible answers. Three passages and four titles to them are offered, i.e. one title is superfluous.

There is also "fill in the gaps" technique that can only be used to develop the ability to read with a full understanding of the information. So, students receive a text in which every N - th word is missing (N - ranges from 5 to 10). The task of the students is to fill in the gaps with suitable words.

Reception "mosaic" involves the division of the "bank of information", i.e. after familiarization with a certain part of the information; students exchange it and restore the general content of the text. "Noting" or "writing short notes" is a work technique aimed at developing the ability to write down briefly in the form of notes the content of the read text in order to record the necessary information for further use [9, p.25]. Such a method of working on the text as "logical rearrangement" or "reconstruction of the sequence" suggests the redistribution of material in a logical sequence or according to a plan. The result of such work is a recreated connected text. A meaningful and semantic choice of answers or judgments can be made using tasks called "true / false statements". The "addition" technique is based on a passage of text or a series of unfinished sentences that must be completed using the information obtained from the read text. This technique is typical for the development of the ability to read the text with a complete understanding of the information.

Conclusion: Thus, in this development, methods and techniques for working on a foreign language text are considered, the choice of which should be guided by the purpose of the lesson, the type of text chosen for reading, as well as the stage of working with it. Moreover, qualitative results in teaching reading can be achieved with using effective methods at different stages of training. The success not only in mastering reading, but also in mastering a foreign language in general, the emergence of interest and conscious motivation for the development and improvement of one's speech competencies depends on how methodically well-chosen teaching techniques are.

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